

AN INNOVATIVE WAY OF CREATING A DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENT IN THE ART CENTER

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Abstract. *In this article, the innovative forms of using non-traditional methods of drawing in the education of preschool children, the pedagogical, organizational-methodical and technological bases of introducing new methods of creating an innovative environment in the educational process aimed at forming children's basic developmental competences are highlighted.*

Keywords: *innovation, graphics, creativity, starch, unusual.*

The French scholar P.Shokar shows in an interesting drawing and content that the hand is considered the main tool of graphic expression in the development of children's visual creativity. Emphasizing the need to teach children graphic expression in the book "A child in schools belonging to mothers from 4 to 5 years old", P. Shokar distinguishes three stages in this process. The first stage consists of a spontaneous (without external influence) drawing process, during which the pedagogue observes the child, determines his drawing skills, evaluates the productivity of his activity and gives feedback.

Introducing the child to the world around him is one of the most important tasks of working with preschool children. An excellent opportunity to achieve this goal includes non-traditional drawings. Today, in order to achieve this result, special attention is being paid to the non-traditional methods of visual activity classes of pre-school educational organizations in "Art" centers.

UNCONVENTIONAL DRAWING METHODS AND THEIR ADVANTAGES

Drawing is a wonderful free time for a preschooler, a work that does not need to be forced. However, it is important to support the child and positively evaluate the results of his creativity.

Expand children's creativity. Traditional drawing teaches the child how to correctly work with brushes, paints, pencils and felt-tip pens, to distinguish between different shapes and colors. Non-traditional drawing techniques help him to be more creative, emotionally stable, confident and active.

"The origins of children's abilities and talents are in your hands. In the fingers, in a figurative sense, there are the best threads - rivers, which are the source of creative thought. In other words, the more skills a child has, the smarter the child will be"

V.A. Sukhomlinsky

Children try to understand the world and express their impressions of it through cognitive and creative activities: playing, drawing, telling. Drawing gives great opportunities here. To give children the opportunity to express themselves in different ways, you can invite your child to draw both in traditional ways and in the most unusual ways. The more interesting the conditions in which the child's graphic activity takes place, the faster his creative abilities develop. Let's see how drawing techniques for children can be used for the development of a child.

Traditional painting technique. The foundation for the general all-round development of the child is laid in the early preschool age. Drawing is one of the most important means of child development, in the process of which the child learns the world and forms an aesthetic attitude towards it.

While drawing, the child develops the most diverse abilities, in particular: the child learns to visually assess the shape of the object, to move in space, to distinguish and feel colors. Exercises the eyes and hands, develops the hand. Do you know that drawing is one of the main methods of a child's all-round development, feelings, fine motor skills of hands, sense of shape and color? With this simple and interesting activity, children express their attitude towards reality. The success of upbringing and education depends on what forms and methods the teacher and parents use in creative activities with the child.

❖ Drawing with a simple pencil;

❖ Drawing with colored pencils;

❖ Drawing with felt-tip pens;

❖ Drawing with a brush - watercolor, gouache

❖ Drawing with wax pencils

Thus, the main technique for younger children is to show them how to use pencils and paints at school age. At the same age, passive drawing is effective in children: when a teacher or parent guides the child's hand, when children grow up a little, visual activity is taught using the method of receiving information: children learn the shape of an object, they trace it with their hands, feel the contours. Studying this topic helps the child to create a complete picture of the topic. The next step is to choose a painting technique.

When choosing drawing techniques for babies, you should pay attention to their age and interest. In order for drawing to be useful and educational, it must first be interesting.

Drawing with paint and pencil

Children love to draw, especially if they are good at it, even drawing using traditional techniques like paint and pencil requires some skill. If there is no skill, then the drawing may not work as intended by the little artist, as a result of which the child may become frustrated and no longer want to draw. Children of small preschool age do not yet have sufficient skills in drawing.

Let's see how you can teach your child to draw with paint and pencil.

As soon as the child learns to hold a brush in his hand, invite him to draw. For the first lessons, it is better to use colored paints: it is not necessary to dilute the paints with so much water that it leaves a bright mark. Show your child a drawing technique such as "gluing": the process of pressing a brush with paint on paper must be applied in an orderly manner. It should be explained about its formation of traces - leaf, light, animal's trace, flower, etc. Children can use this simple method to describe familiar natural phenomena. It will be interesting to draw with dark white gouache on blue paper. So you can describe, say, a snowfall.

The next stage of drawing with paints is the image of straight and wavy lines. Usually, children learn to work with paints and brushes at the age of 3.5 - 4 years. From this age, children can be given paints at his disposal: let him draw what he wants. And parents just need to suggest drawing topics and show the right technique.

Start drawing with a pencil. At first, it is better to give the child a felt-tip pen, not a pencil: because the felt-tip pen leaves a bright mark even when lightly pressed. If the child has a strong hand, give him a pencil. Move your hand together with your child and draw different shapes together. So, little by little, he understands how to move the pencil to get the desired picture. Repeat the movements many times, fix them.

Suggestion. Make your child interested in drawing by creating good conditions for creativity: there should be quality equipment, a separate table and chair in a bright place suitable for the height of the child.

Non-traditional painting techniques are a great way to create small works. It turns out that you can create a great picture, and the palm can turn into a blue elephant. A gray spot can turn into a tree, and potatoes and carrots can surprise with unusual patterns.

For example, it can be used with preschool children:

- * drawing with fingers;
- * drawing with palms;
- * printing from threads;
- * print potatoes or carrots.

With preschoolers, you can try:

- * printed pictures;
- * printing with plasticine;
- * oil pastels + watercolor;
- * leaf traces;
- * pictures of dates;
- * drawing with cotton balls;
- * magic threads;
- * monotype.

And with older preschoolers, you can learn more complex techniques:

- * painting with soap bubbles;
- * drawing with crumpled paper;
- * painting with salt;
- * blotography;
- * plasticineography;
- * grattage;
- * frottage.

Did you know that various non-traditional painting techniques are becoming more popular day by day? In this, children act as they like while drawing. The beauty of the non-traditional drawing technique is that in the creative process, the child can use different methods, different materials and their combinations with pleasure. That's why these drawing methods are so interesting for both children and adults: there are no limits to imagination and self-expression. What combination of materials can be used in painting to make the creative process enjoyable, and the picture turns out to be unusual and expressive. And in preschool educational organizations, non-traditional drawing also brings a lot of positive emotions to children. Let's see what non-traditional drawing methods you can do with children at home and at kindergarten.

Drawing with fingers

For this, a much larger area is needed; it is better to do finger painting with a small group of children. Write names and the date on the back of the glossy, smooth paper without getting wet. Flatten the rolled up papers before the children get to work. Invite the children to wear robes. They should be told that they can draw with their fingers, palms, fists, but not with a brush. The type of activity allows children to "legitimately" engage in painting. Some restrictions may apply. Children accept them as souls, because this type of activity is very interesting. Finger painting can also be done on a table with a specially treated surface. The picture drawn on the table can then be copied on paper. For this, it is enough to put the paper on the picture and press hard. The carving of the table also facilitates this process. It can be organized in different ways. The child dips his fingers in gouache and paints on paper.

Finger painting using cornstarch

- Add one part starch to three parts water;
- Mix the starch in cold water until the round lumps disappear;
- Boil until the clarity and consistency of pudding;
- Add food coloring to the warm mixture;

The involvement of small groups of children in the preparation stage can help in measuring and mixing the necessary doses of the components. (Fig. 2)

Finger painting using potato starch

- One and a half cups of starch;
- Half a cup of soap foam;
- Four cups of boiling water;
- Half a cup of powder;
- Coloring substance.

Mix starch with water until a soft mass is formed. Add the water gradually, while continuing to mix. Cook on low heat until the mixture becomes glossy in color. Before the mixture cools, mix the soap foam into it. After the mixture has cooled, add powder and coloring agent to it.

If you can find non-toxic liquid starch, mix it with an aqueous paint mixture or powder paint.

Finger painting using soap foam

Mix the foam to the level of liquid dough. If you have children who are afraid of getting things dirty, get them involved in making the dough and let them paint with the mixture on a table with a ribbed surface.

A small amount of easily washable color can be added to the mixture prepared for other children. The painted surface of the table can be washed with a sponge.

Painting with soap bubbles

You can draw with soap bubbles. To do this, you need to add any soap solution and paint to a glass of water. Use the tube to fill up a lot of foam. Lean the paper over the bubbles. When the first patterns appear, you can lift the paper. Bubble patterns are ready.

Painting with a sponge

Give different shapes to several sponges using scissors or a knife. Mix egg yolk paint with water and put it in small plates. Children can dip the sponge in paint and press it on the paper. It is possible to simply draw with a sponge. This exercise is very interesting. Over time, children will learn the principle of clicking.

Collect different objects such as buttons, cardboard, cut-out cardboard circles, glue sticks, glass bottles. Place the paint on shallow plastic trays.

Children should completely paint the object of their choice. The teacher can show you how to do it. Children quickly learn the principle and begin to act independently.

Painting with drips

If the children are small, the teacher himself folds the sheets of paper on which they draw pictures in the middle. It is good if the children are also present at this time. They get the idea over time and do all the work themselves. When painting with drips, children fold the paint on one side of a folded sheet of paper and glue one side to the other. When they write a paper, they usually create excellent conditions for developing themselves and overcoming some fears by discussing the picture they see. ("a picture of a bat was created").

Painting with wax

To paint such a picture, children paint the paper thickly with wax. They can even be used as pens. Then the entire picture is covered with an aqueous mixture of paint. The wax prevents the paint from spreading and the image appears against its background. Children often call such pictures magic pictures. The teacher can look at these activities as a scientific experiment.

Non-traditional methods of children's drawing stimulate the development of children's imagination and creative thinking, the manifestation of initiative and independence. In the process of drawing, a preschool child increases his observation skills, forms an individual vision of art and beauty, and tries to create beautiful things.

The use of modern systems is a necessary condition for establishing artistic and aesthetic education. Visual activity is a purposeful process that meets the requirements of the comprehensive and comprehensive development of the child and organizes pedagogical work with children in a single system.

Children's drawings are not simple, they tell you about their mental state, their inner world - their joys and sorrows, experiences and worries that often cannot be expressed in words. By creating works of art, children develop fine motor skills, develop imagination, learn to think, perceive visual aesthetics, and develop a sense of color. In the process of drawing, the lively work of thought, imaginative imagination and artistic taste, observation and visual memory, hand and eye muscle-motor functions are developed. Therefore, it is important to develop the necessary mechanisms for mastering writing at preschool age, to gather movement and practical experience of the child, and to create conditions for the development of manual skills. Art can prevent aggressive behavior. Therefore, our current modern pedagogues should be intelligent and keep pace with the times.

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